

Incentives, Assessment, and the Reliability of Statistical Significance
Examinations of Evidence

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This analysis evaluates how researcher hypothesis selection incentives on the inferential value of empirical analyses. It illustrates the strength with which a “statistically significant” outcome objective incentivizes researcher aversion to testing possibly true null hypotheses in a comparatively unconstrained general setting. Left unfettered, it suggests that settings wherein researchers almost always opt to test false null hypotheses are common. That is, studies routinely produce reliable “falsifications” of *a priori* false hypotheses, a practice that transparently lacks inferential relevance. An outcome that aligns with the longstanding perspective that in many fields and settings the null hypotheses that researchers test are commonly false (e.g., Cohen, 1992). Collectively, the analysis illustrates the importance of comprehensive uncontrived understandings of researcher incentives and research assessment practices when evaluating the reliability and relevance of findings obtained from Null Hypothesis Significance Test based examinations of evidence.

Key words: False Positives, priors, Statistical Significance Based Inference, Methodology

1. Introduction

This analysis addresses how incentives broadly shape variation in the plausibility levels of hypotheses that researchers choose to test. It develops a parsimonious algebraic framework based on a set of minimally restrictive underlying assumptions for determining equilibrium optimal hypothesis plausibility choices. Within this framework the level and nature of resistance to the testing of implausible hypotheses, broadly construed, is pivotal. Absent consequential consistent resistance researchers will gravitate to the testing of highly implausible null hypotheses. That is, researchers will actively seek to test implausible nulls, willingly taking the risk of the occasional call out for engaging in such inherently uninformative research-wasting. In fact, the analysis suggests that researchers will only commonly test plausible null hypotheses under the following sorts of conditions: (1) stringent consistently applied peer/journal resistance to the testing of plausible null hypotheses; (2) a compensation/reward system tied to the testing of hypotheses rather than the outcomes of such tests (e.g., registered reports; quality control); (3) operating in a structurally constrained environment wherein the only nulls available are highly plausible (e.g., a for profit drug discovery enterprise or a lab that's funding depends on the discovery of rare things) as may sometimes typify "hard" science experiments.

As the analysis models researchers pursuing publication of their research efforts in a reputable journal it aligns in several respects with existent models of the research production process such as McElreath and Smaldino (2015, 2016), Higginson and Munafo (2016), and Campbell and Gustafson (2019). Researchers face both environmental and journal-imposed constraints in the pursuit of their publication success objective. These studies, however, focus on inferential reliability outcomes in conditions wherein tested null hypotheses are presumed to be highly plausible. For instance, McElreath and Smaldino (2016), Smaldino et al. (2019), and Wilson and Wixted (2018) all impose a requirement that 9 out of 10 tested null hypotheses be true. Campbell and Gustafson (2019)

do allow researcher choice, but then focus their analysis on settings where conditions favor (arguably compel) researchers to shun testing anything but highly plausible null hypotheses. In contrast, this analysis focuses on how variation in journal resistance to publication on hypothesis implausibility grounds, inclusive of the ineffectiveness of such resistance, shapes researcher hypothesis choices. Among other things, it strongly suggests that journal-based resistance alone is highly unlikely to incentivize researcher pursuit of plausible hypotheses. In fact, a far more likely outcome are equilibria wherein researchers widely and vigorously pursue, and journals publish tests of *a priori* false null hypotheses.¹

Incorporating hypothesis selection incentives in an unconstrained fashion also shifts the conceptual lack of inferential quality away from conventional notions about how the pursuit of significance outcomes “biases” researcher “design, data analysis, and presentation” activities (p. 697, Ioannidis, 2005). That is, given a hypothesis, how the incentive to produce a “statistically significant” outcome adversely influences how researchers conduct and interpret their empirical analyses. Such partial “*ceteris paribus*” understandings largely exclude or severely limit consideration of how such incentives also impact researcher hypothesis choices and the independent assessment of such research. Consequently, one encounters expositions that follow a rather predictable script. Researchers exogenously tasked with testing highly plausible null hypotheses commonly reject true null hypotheses. As statistical significance assessment is inherently error-

¹ This widespread implausibility assertion is seemingly at odds with widespread “evidence” that replication rates are low in many fields. At the empirical level, a key underpinning for such “evidence” is either a statistical significance or a directional consistency standard. The null hypothesis plausibility relevance of such standards, however, requires the imposition of a restrictive parametrization of the alternative hypothesis. That is, tested nulls are generally plausible if the effect equals zero **and** the only considered alternative is that it equals something substantively different from 0. A Cohen’s *d* of .2 for instance. Missing from this picture is the possibility that the true parameter value might instead be somewhere in between, a Cohen’s *d* of say .01 for instance. If so, the null is false, not true, but absent compelling research design power the replication outcome distribution for $d = .01$ will be nigh on indistinguishable from what would occur if *d* really is 0 (Vu, 2024). That is, replication rates will be similarly low when effect sizes are either generally zero or when they are generally non-zero but small. Moreover, just to be clear, the significance testing framework mandates an exact specification of the tested null hypothesis (Cready, 2025). There is no wiggle room in it for asserting that .01 can be re-understood as equaling zero. If one wishes to test whether an effect is less than or equal to .01 then one should do so directly, not engage in bait and switch doublespeak.

prone, the prevalence of such “false positive” outcomes increases with the odds that the assigned-for testing-hypothesis is true. So, in the extreme, published findings are almost always false and outcome success incentives greatly worsen things (Ioannidis, 2005).

By relaxing the “imposed hypothesis” component of this picture this analysis arrives at its very different understanding of the relation between incentives and false positive prevalence that is likely to typify many fields. Simply put, it brings forward as a first order effect the commonsense notion that when researchers can achieve research success from the study of implausible null hypotheses they will do so. As, *ceteris paribus*, the odds of obtaining a “statistical significance” outcome increases with the odds that the tested null hypothesis is false. Such a preference for testing false hypotheses necessarily attenuates the odds of obtaining false positive outcomes. In the extreme, it effectively eliminates them. Moreover, while it is generally recognized that testing almost surely false null hypotheses lacks inferential relevance, it is also the case that such seemingly fruitless testing happens far more often than we care to fully acknowledge ((e.g., Berkson, 1938; Tukey, 1991; De Long and Lang, 1992; Cohen, 1994; Gelman and Carlin, 2017; Cready, 2025). In this regard, the analysis illustrates that from an incentives perspective such prevalence is not a matter of happenstance. It is an equilibrium outcome that flows from an absence of vigorous resistance to studies addressing such hypotheses.

With respect to implausibility resistance’s central role in things the analysis also illustrates how weak resistance largely negates commonly voiced concerns regarding the vulnerability of “statistical significance” identifications to researcher misbehavior. A collection of significance test assessments of almost surely false hypotheses is constitutionally incapable of producing false positives in numbers no matter what sorts of statistical shenanigans underlie them. In fact, putting up further barriers targeting the integrity of such identifications may worsen things. Mandating the provision of further supportive evidence from hold-out samples, cross-sectional validations,

alternative model specifications or sample designs does little in terms of improving reliability but markedly increases the attractiveness of testing false nulls. That is, it incentivizes irrelevant pursuits. Similarly, the analysis illustrates how absence of intentional replication in a field of study is reasonably understood as evidencing implausibility resistance ineffectiveness. Replication does not happen because absent effective resistance a field's tested null hypotheses are almost always false, making the undertaking of such exercises highly undesirable, all the more when conditions broadly favor the testing of implausible null hypotheses.

While the analysis directly concerns null hypothesis testing, as defined by Principle 1 of *The American Statistical Association Statement of Statistical Significance and P Values* (in Wasserstein and Lazar, 2016; and henceforth identified as the *ASA Statement*), it does have implications for the study of implausible alternative (to the null) "research hypotheses".² When resistance to the testing of implausible nulls is sufficient to discourage interest in them, researchers necessarily shift their attention to more plausible nulls. Such a shift brings implausible research hypotheses into the picture since a plausible null implies an implausible research hypothesis. However, while a plausible null implies an implausible research hypothesis it is not the case that an implausible research hypothesis necessarily implies a plausible null hypothesis. The null could be implausible for reasons other than that encompassed by a study's research hypothesis. Consequently, it is also the case that the clever researcher has a particular interest in coupling tests of implausible null hypotheses with motivations pertaining to doubt-worthy research hypotheses. By so doing they leverage doubts about a study's research hypothesis to cast unwarranted credibility to the highly implausible null hypothesis they actually test.

² Principle 1 of the *ASA Statement* in full reads as follows: "**P-values can indicate how incompatible the data are with a specified statistical model.** A *p*-value provides one approach to summarizing the incompatibility between a particular set of data and a proposed model for the data. The most common context is a model, constructed under a set of assumptions, together with a so-called "null hypothesis." Often the null hypothesis postulates the absence of an effect, such as no difference between two groups, or the absence of a relationship between a factor and an outcome. The smaller the *p*-value, the greater the statistical incompatibility of the data with the null hypothesis, if the underlying assumptions used to calculate the *p*-value hold. This incompatibility can be interpreted as casting doubt on or providing evidence against the null hypothesis or underlying assumptions."

2. Model

The analysis relies on a simplified model of a research process that starts (period 1) with the researcher arriving at a hypothesis that's distinguishing feature is the likelihood that it is untrue (F). The researcher then conducts a single null hypothesis significance test of this hypothesis and obtains a p-value outcome for it (period 2). In the final period the researcher submits this finding to the journal (which can also be taken as representative of a field of study) which decides whether or not to publish it based on its: (1) p-value falling below the journal's established statistical significance threshold value, α ; and, (2) its perceived "contribution". Building on the basic significance success framework presented in Wacholder et al. (2004) and Ionnidis (2005) I model the likelihood of a publication success (S_LHOOD) under these conditions as:

$$S_LHOOD = (\alpha + F \times Z \times (1 - \alpha)) \times G(F, y) \quad (1).$$

Where:

$G(F, y)$ is bounded between 0 and 1 and is an inverse measure of the resistance researchers face to the publication of statistically significant outcomes based on F and, importantly, a vector of other factors (y) such as importance of the research topic area, research design novelty, hot topic status, design integrity, who it cites, reputations of its authors, etc.);

Z in this expression aligns with the conventional $(1 - \beta)$ measure of power. It differs in that $(1 - \beta)$ reflects overall false null identification efficacy inclusive of that provided by α while Z only reflects efficacy incremental to that provided by α . In this sense the analysis divides $(1 - \beta)$ into two parts: Z and αF where Z encompasses research design features such as sample size along with the magnitude by which the studied parameter value "truly" differs from the tested null hypothesis value for it.

As allowing for publication of an article based purely on the y values of this expression potentially trivialize F's role in the publication process (i.e., researchers will simply pursue high F

hypotheses and ride the y vector to research success) the analysis models $G(F,y)$ as the product of a (necessary for analytical tractability) summarization of how the vector of y values, $G(y)$, collectively factor into publication prospects and $(1 - r \times J(F))$:

$$G(F,y) = ((1 - r \times J(F)) * G(y)) \quad (2).$$

$J(F)$ captures a hypothetical perfectly applied journal resistance standard for publication based on certain knowledge of F . The r scalar ranges from between 1 and 0 and measures the consistency or strength with which the journal applies $J(F)$. In the interests of analytical tractability and conceptual simplicity the analysis models $J(F)$ as equaling F . Hence, at $r = 100\%$ resistance rises directly with F , the journal never publishes articles testing surely false null hypotheses and absence any resistance ($r = 0\%$) F never explicitly factors into its publications decisions.

In general, r should fall below 100% because of systematic underweighting and lapses in journal application of the $J(F)$ criterion. Underweighting occurs for at least two reasons (additional reasons are discussed later in the analysis). First, F is commonly amorphous. While most everyone can come up with ideas about F , rare is the setting where such ideas are coupled with rigid quantification or consensus. Consequently, in perception at least, F is commonly noisy, and it is well known that a criterion's decision-making weight declines as its noisiness rises. Second, journal assessment processes are, as most anyone who has been through one can attest, highly idiosyncratic. So, it follows that on a submission by submission basis idiosyncrasy has its way a journal's implausibility resistance efficacy, even to the point that implausibility never enters the assessment picture in some cases. Hence, even though the journal's r may often come close to 100%, the average (or in expectation) resistance level is quite a bit further away from 100%.

The r scalar can also encompass r as varying depending on F . In fact, many of the existent engagements with the academic publication production process implicitly model r as being conditional on the value of F . For instance, the rather commonly employed specification wherein F

is set equal to some value (V) based on what might best be described as speculative understandings of problematic evidence (see fn. 1) can be modeled as setting r equal to 1/F whenever $F > V$ and 0 otherwise. Relatedly, r is also interpretable as capturing how F-relevant factors outside of the formal journal assessment process influence hypothesis choices. For instance, in fields of study that might be broadly characterized as tasked with searching for “breakthrough discoveries” (Campbell and Gustafson, 2019) regarding recognized “important” problems (e.g., “search for the cure,” “find the cause”, “locate the effect”, “find the polymorphism”) the researcher may routinely encounter hypothesis choice sets wherein all candidate null hypotheses are low F. That is, they are environmentally constrained or incentivized rather than journal resistance intensity constrained to the testing of low F hypotheses. Similarly, researchers may be explicitly incentivized to test implausible null for reasons other than journal publications such as being paid to do so or to win jackpot payouts from discovering rare things. One might model (environmental) resistance intensity in such a circumstance as r rapidly rising to 1 well before F gets to 1, or even to .1.

Given this understanding of r, J(F), and H(y) I now return to journal assessment in the form of a constrained maximization exercise based on equation (1). Substitution of (2) into (1) under the further assumption that $J(F) = F$ produces the following linear expression for the likelihood of publication success based on the values taken by r, F, Z, and α :

$$S_LHOOD = ((\alpha + FxZx(1 - \alpha)) - ((\alpha + FxZx(1 - \alpha))xrxF))xH(y) \quad (3),$$

Wherein

$$\delta S_LHOOD/\delta F = ((Zx(1 - \alpha)x(1 - 2rxF)) - rx\alpha)H(y) \quad (3a)$$

$$\delta S_LHOOD/\delta r = - ((\alpha + FxZ(1 - \alpha))F)H(y) < 0 \quad (3b)$$

$$\delta S_LHOOD/\delta Z = F(1 - \alpha)x(1 - rF)xH(y) > 0 \quad (3c)$$

While S_LHOOD decreases with r and increases with Z, its relationship with F may be positive or negative depending on whether favorable impact on the prospect of a statistical significance outcome

outweighs loss of hypothesis rejection “surprise” content. Under such conditions the unique F that maximizes S_{LHOOD} conditional on Z , r , and α equals:

$$F_m = 1/(2r) - \alpha/(2(1-\alpha)xZ), \quad 0 \leq F_m \leq 1 \quad (4),$$

Which, in turn varies with Z , r and α as follows:

$$\delta F_m / \delta Z = \alpha / (2(1-\alpha)xZ^2) > 0 \quad (4a)$$

$$\delta F_m / \delta r = -1 / (2r^2) < 0 \quad (4b)$$

$$\delta F_m / \delta \alpha = -1 / (2Zx(1-\alpha)^2) < 0 \quad (4c)^3.$$

That is, increasing test power increases the attractiveness of testing false hypotheses while increasing resistance intensity or relaxing significance thresholds decreases such attractiveness. The fact that r is a denominator in (4) also means that as it approaches 0, F_m approaches infinity. As F 's natural maximum is 1, it follows that F reaches this maximum well before r reaches zero. In fact, F attains this maximum when

$$r < (1-\alpha)xZ / (2(1-\alpha)xZ + \alpha) \quad (5).$$

On the other hand, when the journal robustly resists the publication of studies addressing implausible nulls (i.e., r near 1) then success maximization lies in the direction of plausible nulls. For instance, substituting $r = 1$ into (4) yields:

$$F_m (r=1) = 1/2 - \alpha / (2(1-\alpha)xZ) < 50\% \quad (6).$$

That is, when the journal vigorously and consistently resists the publication of studies addressing implausible nulls then studies concerning hypotheses that are more likely to be true than to be false will have better publication prospects than comparable (measured as absolute distance from 50%) more likely false than true hypotheses.

³ The derivation holds Z constant under the assumption that as α changes researchers hypothesis choices change in such a manner that Z remains constant. Such an assumption is feasible as hypothesis choice is not held constant in this framework. A more comprehensive specification would further incorporate a conjectured change in Z offset (i.e., $dZ/d\alpha$) that would reflect the idea that as α decreases (increases) the availability of high Z hypotheses declines (expands). It seems unlikely, however, that the magnitude of this offset would alter the overall direction of the relation in conventional research design conditions.

3. Applications

In this section I apply the model to describe research conduct and outcomes under alternative perspectives of how researchers arrive at the hypotheses they happen to test. Initially, in line with conventional engagements with significance testing's inferential drawbacks, I describe outcomes that follow when the researcher lacks the ability to select on F . Hence, it aligns with commonly encountered assessments of the reliability and relevance of the academic research process based on imposed priors for tested hypotheses. I then evaluate how relaxing this constraint alters research process outcomes.

At the conduct-of-research level, henceforth identified as the research frontier, the analysis reports expected type I and type II error rates experienced by researchers at varying levels of Z (power), conditional on the mechanism that determines hypothesis F levels. In the case of endogenous selection, endogenously determined F is reported as well. A further frontier outcome of particular interest is the ratio of type I to type II error. Two broad assumptions about type II errors impact significance testing's inferential integrity: (1) that they are not highly likely (i.e., the design has reasonable ability to discriminate between false and true nulls); and, (2) that they are not rare relative to "controlled" type I error rates. The reported type II error percentages concern the second of these. A high ratio value means that those inferential errors that do occur are almost always type I errors, a condition that gives rise to the possibility that a statistically significant rejection of a null hypothesis strengthens the case for the null being true rather than false (a defining attribute of the Jeffreys-Lindley paradox).⁴ A high ratio also informs the ideas that significance testing exhibits a "bias against the null" and the value of tightening significance thresholds as test power increases.

The analysis also pushes matters through to the journal content implications that follow from whatever process researchers arrive at the hypotheses they test. Here the focus is on journal test-of-

⁴ The paradox originates in the writings of Jeffreys (1935, 1936a, 1936b) and is subsequently extended by Lindley (1957). See Wagenmakers and Ly (2023) for a comprehensive discussion.

hypothesis novelty content and the prevalence with which it publishes articles reporting “false positives”. Importantly, novelty content in this context refers to the inferential relevance of evidence suggesting that the tested null hypotheses is not true. Hence, I measure it as $1 - F_j$, where F_j is the expected average F level of the set of studies published by the journal. This targeted focus on hypothesis novelty directly follows from the limits on p-value interpretation laid out by the principles contained in the *ASA Statement*. Novelty, so defined, does not encompass other potential drivers of research interest such as the provision of effect size estimates (inclusive of economic, behavioral, or clinical significance assessment), newness of the topic, provocativeness of the advanced alternative hypothesis, or improved measurement of a studied phenomenon of interest. Such factors are reflected in $H(y)$. As the primary interest here is how variation in F and r incremental to variation in $H(y)$ affects research outcomes, $H(y)$ is set equal to 1 for all hypotheses.⁵

3.1 Exogenous Selection

Criticisms of conventional significance test assessment inferential reliability broadly rely on either an explicit or implicit constraint that tested hypotheses are rarely false. Such a “skeptical priors” understanding aligns with the view that a tested null hypothesis represents accepted, conventional, or reasonably expected to hold understanding of a phenomenon whereas the considered research hypothesis alternative to it is the clear underdog. These sorts of “skeptical priors” also align with most existent models of the research production process exogenously impose on researchers (e.g., Ioannidis, 2005; Button et al., 2013; Smaldino and McElreath, 2016; Smaldino et al., 2019).

Panel A of table 1 reflects expected research frontier and journal content outcomes when skeptical priors are extreme (1 out of every 100 tested hypotheses is false) and moderate (1 out of every 4 tested hypotheses is false). Appendix A elaborates on the calculations of these values. At

⁵ It is of some relevance that journal rejection rates vary inversely with $H(y)$. Hence, observed publication rates can be low or high irrespective of F^m .

extreme skepticism overall errors are low, around 5%, and are practically invariant with respect to power level. Yields (odds of obtaining significance success) are also low. Ratios of type I to type II error, on the other hand, alarmingly slant in the type I error direction, indicating that tightening α would reduce overall error and improve inferential reliability. Consistent with this deterioration in type I error control journal false positive account abounds, exceeding 80% irrespective of test power. An outcome that aligns with an abundance of existent analyses illustrating the extreme unreliability of significance-based inference when tested nulls are almost always true (e.g., Ioannidis, 2005).

At the 1 in 4 level journal content matters improve considerably. Researchers produce significance outcomes with greater frequency and these outcomes are more reliable. Test power is particularly critical, as moving Z from 30% to 80% doubles yields and halves false positive percentages. This outcome aligns with evidence presented in studies such as Button et al. (2013) and Higginson and Munafo (2016) which illustrate the power's determinative role for the reliability of significance outcomes when tested nulls are commonly true (e.g., $F < 30\%$) but not almost always true (e.g., $F < 5\%$). Higginson and Munafo, in fact, argue that in these circumstances researchers may find it beneficial to lower the power of their tests to free up resources to increase the number of hypotheses they test. As will become evident in some of the later analysis this sort of incentive rapidly dissipates as F rises above the 50% mark.

A somewhat different view of F is that priors be taken as neutral—the null is just as likely to be true as it is to be false. Support for this perspective stems from the “principle of insufficient reason” or “principle of indifference,” that's origins (though not its formal identification) can be traced back to the writings of Laplace. When applied to priors, this principle suggests that when relative likelihoods across outcomes are unknown, one should treat every possible outcome as equally probable. In simpler terms, the prior can be thought of as a random draw from a uniform distribution ranging from zero to 1.

Table 1
Research Frontier and Journal Content Outcomes Under Exogenous Priors

Panel A: Skeptical Priors								
	<u>1 out of 100 Hypotheses is False</u>				<u>1 out of 4 Hypotheses is False</u>			
	Z				Z			
	30%	50%	80%	99.9%	30%	50%	80%	99.9%
Frontier								
Overall Error	5.6%	5.4%	5.1%	5.0%	20.4%	15.6%	8.5%	3.8%
Type II Error	0.67%	0.48%	0.19%	~0%	16.63%	11.88%	4.75%	0.02%
Type I Error	4.95%	4.95%	4.95%	4.95%	3.75%	3.75%	3.75%	3.75%
Type I/II	7.4	10.4	26.1	5,211	0.2	0.3	0.8	157.9
Yield	5.3%	5.5%	5.8%	5.9%	12.1%	16.9%	24.0%	28.7%
Journal								
Hyp. Novelty	99%	99%	99%	99%	75%	75%	75%	75%
False Positive	93.7%	90.4%	85.9%	83.2%	30.9%	22.2%	15.6%	13.1%
Panel B: Neutral/Uninformed 50-50 Priors								
	Z							
	30%		50%		80%		99.9%	
	r=0%	r=100%	r=0%	r=100%	r=0%	r=100%	r=0%	r=100%
Frontier								
Overall Error	35.8%	35.8%	26.3%	26.3%	12.0%	12.0%	2.5%	2.5%
Type II Error	33.3%	33.3%	23.8%	23.8%	9.5%	9.5%	0.05%	0.05%
Type I Error	2.5%	2.5%	2.5%	2.5%	2.5%	2.5%	2.5%	2.5%
Type I/II	0.075	0.075	0.042	0.042	0.263	0.263	50	50
Yield	19.3%	19.3%	28.8%	28.8%	43.0%	43.0%	52.5%	52.5%
Journal								
Hyp. Novelty	37.7%	51.9%	36.2%	51.3%	35.3%	50.9%	34.9%	50.8%
False Positive	13.0%	23.0%	8.7%	16.0%	5.8%	11.0%	4.8%	9.1%

Panel B of table 1 provides the research frontier and journal content outcomes when F has a uniform distribution across the set of tested hypotheses. Unlike panel A where priors for all tested hypotheses equal exogenously imposed F, allowing F to vary means that journal implausibility resistance matters for journal content. Accordingly, panel B reports frontier and content outcomes conditional on the absence ($r = 0$) or presence in full ($r=100\%$) of journal implausibility resistance

intensity. As hypotheses are exogenously imposed, researchers lack the ability to select hypotheses based on F , so resistance intensity only matters for journal content and has no differential impact on frontier outcomes. Of particular interest are the close to 100% increases in false positive content levels that occur when journals shift from a no resistance mindset to applying resistance in full. That is, applying resistance causes false positives, holding researcher actions constant. This resistance causality consequence broadly informs settings wherein implausibility resistance exists on the part of the journal, but researchers are somehow desensitized to it when selecting hypotheses. One such rather familiar setting where this happens is multiple comparisons. That is, when a research investigation facilitates the testing of hypotheses in numbers (e.g., Gelman and Loken, 2014). I elaborate on the model's implications for such bundling of hypothesis tests later in the analysis.

These research frontier outcomes also considerably differ from those presented in panel A. Type 2 error rates are higher while overall error rates are higher apart from when power is extreme. The lower type I error rates, also observed in the panel A extreme power comparative outcomes, reflect the fact that tests of neutral prior hypotheses produce fewer type I errors than do tests of skeptical prior (of being false) hypotheses. At extreme power, type II errors disappear, leaving type I error as the primary determinant of overall error levels. Also, unlike the skeptical prior outcomes, the type I to type II error ratio is well below 1 in all but the extreme power condition. Hence, under neutral priors obtaining overall error reduction from tightening significance thresholds seems limited to hypotheses tested with extremely high-power designs. Journal novelty content also declines under neutral relative to skeptical priors and consequentially false positive prevalence declines as well.

A further aspect of the reported journal content outcomes of considerable interest concerns their sensitivity to implausibility resistance level. Absent resistance, novelty content drops into the 35% to 38% range, substantially lower than what might expect to hold given that researchers are testing hypotheses that, on average, are true half the time. This drop reflects how resistance intensity

on the part of the journal interacts with hypothesis plausibility level. The odds of obtaining a significance outcome moves inversely with the odds that the null is true. Consequently, tests of less plausible nulls meet the journal's statistical significance threshold more often than do tests of more plausible nulls and end up dominating journal content. Of greater interest, however, is the fact that introducing journal implausibility resistance moves novelty content back to the around 50% level. Hence, resistance produces a journal that's contents align with the hypotheses researchers encounter at the research frontier and largely neutralizes the outcome advantages (in terms of odds of obtaining "statistical significance") to testing implausible rather than plausible hypotheses. That said, it bears repeating that these benefits come at a cost—a near doubling of false positive content.

3.2 Endogenous Selection

Thus far, and consistent with a vast body of existing work addressing the integrity of null hypothesis significance test inference, the analysis treats hypothesis implausibility as exogenous. A researcher takes the hypothesis allotted to them and dutifully tests it. Facing a hypothesis with a 1 in 100 chance of being false they simply carry on in the hopes of obtaining a highly unlikely to manifest rejection outcome that, in the unlikely event that it does manifest, is an odds favorite for turning out to be a false positive. This section and those that follow depart from this exogeneous F convention. Instead of presuming that researchers simply accept whatever Fs fate allots them, it adopts the perspective that, absent other considerations, they actively avoid testing of hypotheses such as those with a 1 in 100 chance of being true that provide little promise of producing successful outcomes and instead search out hypotheses with the greater success potential.

Under such incentives and in line with the presented model of the research process, *ceteris paribus*, researchers choose to test hypotheses with priors of being false equal to F^m as determined by (4). The feasibility of researchers selecting F^m , in expectation, hypotheses depends on a number of further conditions including: (1) wide availability of hypotheses of varying priors of being false

accompanied by researcher freedom to choose from among them; (2) researcher ability to form informed priors regarding hypothesis F levels; and, (3) exclusion of F-dependent payoffs or penalties beyond what is captured by r , Z , and α . None of these conditions need fully hold for the presented outcomes to go through as identifying how selection broadly shapes research outcomes. Limits on hypothesis choices shift the exercise into a constrained by available Fs maximization exercise where researchers prefer those hypotheses with Fs closest to F^m . Noisy priors moderate researcher effectiveness in at identifying F^m hypotheses, but do not alter their interest in selecting them. F-dependent penalties and payoffs can be subsumed into an expanded understanding of r . Under this view r might encompass funding of research proposals to incentivize researchers to take on plausible nulls, heightened reputational or citation count payoff for novel relative to unsurprising findings, the heightened false positive risk posed by testing highly novel hypotheses, restrictions on available for testing hypotheses, and altruistic satisfaction from discovering new things.

Table 2 presents research outcomes under such endogenous selection for the determination of F^m and the research frontier and journal content outcomes when: (1) the journal does not resist publication on implausibility grounds at all (i.e., $r = 0\%$); and, (2) the journal resistance perfectly fully resists publication in direct proportion to F (i.e., $r = 100\%$). Unsurprisingly, absent resistance hypothesis surprise content and, hence, its inferential relevance is non-existent. Researchers routinely pursue the most implausible hypotheses available. Moreover, the reported corner solution values suggest that this inferential wasteland manifests in the face of resistance intensity levels as high as 45%. The $r = 100\%$ outcomes, on the other hand, illustrate the inferential payoff to intense consistent resistance. Researchers choose to test hypotheses that are more often true than false. Consequently, journal novelty content ranges from 52.7% (extreme power) to 58.8%. (low power). As was true under exogenous selection, this novelty content comes at a type I error price. At the research frontier level this price takes the form of type I errors outnumbering type 2 errors by a 53 to 1 margin at the

99.9% power level, raising Jeffreys-Lindley paradox integrity of significance outcomes concern. At the journal outcome level, however, it is at low power, not extreme power that false positive prevalence is high, amounting to nearly one out of every 5 articles at the 30% power level. So, yes the Jeffreys-Lindley paradox is a factor at high power levels, but its journal content reliability implications are negligible.

Table 2
Selection under No and Full Implausibility Resistance

	Z							
	30%		50%		80%		99.9%	
	r=0	r=100%	r=0	r=100%	r=0	r=100%	r=0	r=100%
Frontier								
Implausibility	100%	41.2%	100%	44.7%	100%	46.7%	100%	47.3%
Overall Error	66.5%	30.4%	47.5%	24.0%	19%	11.5%	0.1%	2.7%
Type II Error	66.5%	27.4%	47.5%	21.3%	19%	8.9%	0.1%	0.05%
Type I Error	0%	3.0%	0%	2.7%	0%	2.6%	0%	2.6%
Type I/II	0	0.109	0	0.127	0	0.292	0	53
Yield	33.5%	16.7%	52.5%	26.2%	81.0%	40.5%	99.9%	49.9%
Journal								
Hyp. Novelty	0%	58.8%	0%	55.3%	0%	53.3%	0%	52.7%
False Positive	0%	17.5%	0%	10.5%	0%	6.6%	0%	5.3%
Corner r	45.9%		47.5%		48.4%		48.7%	

Table 2's full resistance research frontier outcomes closely align with those obtained under neutral priors in conjunction with full resistance reported in table 1. As significance testing is thought to perform reasonably well under neutral priors, this broad similarity in outcomes is noteworthy. It suggests that neutral prior-like conditions can arise as an endogenous outcome from the application of robust implausibility resistance. In fact, journal outcome values under endogenous selection improve on those obtained under neutral priors. Specifically, and at odds with the general inverse relation between implausibility levels, novelty content is higher and false positive prevalence is lower under endogenous selection relative to what occurs under exogenous neutral priors-based

selection. This occurs because under endogenous selection researchers' hypothesis choices conform to journal implausibility resistance effectiveness.

3.3 Other Resistance Intensity Outcomes

While ineffectual resistance and 100% resistance constitute two salient extremes for understanding how resistance intensity broadly shapes the relevance and reliability of journal content, what happens between these extremes is of considerable interest as well. In this regard table 3 reports researcher frontier and journal outcomes for two levels of partial/ imperfect resistance intensity: $r=50%$ and $r=75%$.

Table 3
Partial Resistance Implications

	Z							
	30%		50%		80%		99.9%	
	r=50%	r=75%	r=50%	r=75%	r=50%	r=75%	r=50%	r=75%
Frontier								
Implausibility	91.2%	57.9%	94.7%	61.4%	96.7%	63.4%	97.4%	64.0%
Overall Error	61.1%	40.6%	45.0%	31.1%	18.4%	13.9%	0.1%	1.9%
Type II Error	60.7%	38.5%	45.0%	29.2%	18.4%	12.0%	0.1%	0.06%
Type I Error	0.4%	2.1%	~0%	1.9%	~0%	1.9%	~0%	1.8%
Type I/II	0.001	0.055	0.006	0.065	0.009	0.158	1.421	29.3
Yield	31.0%	21.5%	50.0%	34.2%	78.5%	53.2%	97.4%	65.7%
Journal								
Hyp. Novelty	8.8%	42.1%	5.3%	38.6%	3.3%	36.6%	2.6%	36.0%
False Positive	1.4%	9.8%	0.5%	5.6%	0.2%	3.4%	0.1%	2.7%

At 75% resistance journal novelty content drops below 50%, reaching a low of 36% when test power is extreme. However, all in all, it seems a level that provides a balance between false positive risk and novelty content that many journals would likely find acceptable. However, when resistance falls to 50%, novelty content vanishes, ranging from 8.8% (low power) to a scant 2.2% (extreme power). False positive prevalence also declines relative to full resistance. At 50% resistance false positives are practically non-existent when power is at or above 50%. It is also noteworthy that

under extreme power the Type II % is much higher at 50% resistance (41.3%) than it is at 75% resistance (2.6%) and 100% resistance (1.7% in table 2 or 3.9% in table 4). This substantial increase reflects the importance of tested hypothesis plausibility to the manifestation of Jeffreys- Lindley Paradox conditions. Or, going to the source, vigorous implausibility resistance seems a vital prerequisite to the relevance of Jeffreys-Lindley paradox concerns regarding the integrity of statistical significance outcomes.

While 100 % is an intuitive bound on r , nothing precludes a journal from pushing its $J(F)$ above 1. In other words, a journal can compensate for inability to execute r at a suitable level by ramping up $J(F)$ so as to structurally super-resist research submissions addressing implausible nulls. A super-resistance $J(F)$ of particular interest sets the elimination from consideration bar at $F = 50\%$ by doubling F (i.e., $J(F) = 2 \times F$) to counterbalance r being less than 100%. That is, unless the odds in favor the tested null being true exceed those of the alternative hypothesis of research interest being true, the journal rejects the submission. Such a bar corresponds to the commonly encountered idea that the null represents the established thinking or understanding that is only to be abandoned in favor of compelling evidence against it. Moreover, implementing it is straightforward. One need only make a judgement as to which of two hypotheses (null or research) is the more plausible and take that hypothesis as a study's "effective null".

Table 4 presents research frontier and journal content outcomes under this null being more likely true than false resistance threshold. Predictably, such resistance greatly enhances novelty content at the price of increased false positive prevalence and higher Type I/II ratios. A journal or field of study seeking to implement such super resistance should likely consider tightening p-value thresholds and proactive actions to encourage replicative robustness and generalizability assessment

of published findings (Cready, 2021).⁶

Table 4
Super-Resistance-More Likely True than False Resistance Threshold

J(F) = 2F; r=100%.		Z			
		30%	50%	80%	99.9%
Research Frontier					
Implausibility		16.2%	19.7%	21.7%	22.4%
Overall Error		15.0%	13.4%	8.0%	3.9%
Type II Error		10.8%	9.4%	4.1%	0.02%
Type I Error		4.2%	4.0%	3.9%	3.88%
Type I/II Ratio		0.39	0.43	0.95	194
Journal					
Hypothesis Novelty		83.8%	80.3%	78.3%	77.6%
False Positive %		43.5%	27.9%	18.2%	14.8%
Corner r		23.0%	23.8%	24.2%	24.4%

4. Resistance Inhibitors

The presented analysis identifies a setting wherein the journal in making its publication choices seeks to apply implausibility resistance intensity at a level that provides a desired balance between test of hypothesis novelty content and false positive prevalence. In this section I incorporate into the baseline model several fundamentally broadly present structural factors that adversely impact the journal’s implausibility resistance effectiveness. Such factors provide a structural basis for understanding why the widespread testing of, at best, highly implausible null hypotheses in many research disciplines is very much a structurally dictated norm (Cohen, 1994; De Long and Lang, 1992, Cready, 2025).

⁶ Tables 2 through 4 model resistance intensity as a scalar. As an alternative, Appendix B provides journal outcomes when $r = F$. Salient outcomes are remarkably similar for this alternative resistance increasing at an increasing rate with F specification choice. On the other hand, specifications where resistance intensity decreases at an increasing rate to a zero baseline such as those Campbell and Gustafson (2019) focus on will, by construction, dictate the testing of highly plausible hypotheses. The effect being much the same as what occurs in models where r shifts from 0 to 1 when F exceeds some close to zero threshold level or, on the less draconian side, journals effectively super-resist the publication of studies addressing implausible nulls.

4.1 F-Hacking

F, the odds that the tested null is false, is rarely a readily ascertainable number. Beliefs about its value or value range will commonly vary. Consequently, it follows that journal assessment of it is open to influence. Moreover, journals also commonly rely on the submission itself to make the case for publishing the study inclusive of the inferential relevance of tested hypothesis(es). Under these conditions the researcher possesses the motive, means, and opportunity to influence journal perception of F downward. That is researchers F-Hack their hypotheses by maximizing:

$$S_LHOOD_i = ((\alpha + Z_{\alpha}F_{\alpha}(1 - \alpha)) - (\alpha + Z_{\alpha}F_{\alpha}(1 - \alpha))r_{\alpha}(F-M))_{\alpha}H(y) \quad (7)$$

where M reflects the extent of researcher F hacking success. This shifts the implausibility maximization point to

$$F^m_Hack = 1/(2r) - \alpha/(2(1-\alpha)_{\alpha}Z) + M/2 \quad (8).$$

Given that M is positive, such resistance hacking increases the equilibrium hypothesis implausibility level. Moreover, since its magnitude also varies across the opportunity set of hypotheses available for testing by the researcher it further follows that researchers gravitate toward selecting higher M-potential hypotheses while avoiding lower M-potential hypotheses. That is, they search out implausible hypotheses where F-hacking seems likely to succeed and avoid hypotheses where it is apt to fail (i.e., where implausibility is transparently obvious as in a test of the hypothesis that $2 - 1 = 0$). That is, and in contrast with the Smaldino and McElreath (2016) illustration of how absence of skill and effort in conducting empirical analyses degrade inferential quality, here it is the case that researcher application of skill and effort in selecting and pitching hypotheses drives reduction in inferential quality.

4.2 Inflated Significance Understandings

The *ASA Statement's* preamble indicates that the principles it promulgates stem from an understanding that inflated understandings of statistical significance abound among practitioners

of statistics and across fields that rely on significance testing to draw inferences from empirical evidence. That is, researchers and journals commonly attribute inferential relevance or importance to a significance outcome that goes far beyond what it achieves—the identification of incompatibility between the examined evidence and a proposed model (null hypothesis) for what produced it. In fact, three of the six *ASA Statement* principles (Principles 2, 5, and 6) directly target ways researchers inflate the importance of statistical significance outcomes in this manner.

Inflated significance understanding undermines resistance effectiveness by factoring up the significance outcome term (the first term in equation (3)). Hence, success likelihood is

$$S_LHOOD = ((\alpha + Z_x F_x(1 - \alpha))_x(1+S) - (\alpha + Z_x F_x(1 - \alpha))_x r F)_x H(y) \quad (9)$$

where $S > 0$ reflects journal over-attribution of importance to significance identifications. Rearranging terms illustrates the direct impact of attributing unwarranted importance to significance outcomes on resistance:

$$S_LHOOD = ((\alpha + Z_x((F_x(1 - \alpha)) - (\alpha + Z_x F_x(1 - \alpha))_x(rF - S))_x H(y) \quad (10)$$

Consequently, F^m increases even though r remains unchanged:

$$F^m_Sig_Infl = 1/(2r) - \alpha/(2(1-\alpha)_x Z) + S/(2r) \quad (11).$$

4.3 Multiple Journals

The analysis determines F^m in a single journal setting which inherently limits the researcher to a single shot at obtaining a publication outcome based on the hypothesis they choose to test. Introducing a second journal provides them with a second shot. In effect, a second chance at clearing a journal's noisy resistance threshold. The availability of such second chance scoring opportunities allow researchers to exploit the noise in journal F assessments or inconsistency in applying r to achieve publication success from tests of highly implausible null hypotheses. In the two journal setting, for instance, noise in F implies that journal i 's assessment of F , F_i , generally differs from journal j 's assessment, F_j . (Both assessments, however, may be unbiased estimates of F .) Under these

conditions the researcher seeks to maximize:

$$S_LHOOD_i = ((\alpha + Z_x F_x(1 - \alpha)) - (\alpha + Z_x F_x(1 - \alpha))r_x \min(F_i, F_j)) \times H(y) \quad (12)$$

Setting $\min(F_i, F_j)$ to equal a scalar multiple of F such that $\min(F_i, F_j) = m \times F$ leads to the following solution to the researcher's hypothesis success maximization problem:

$$F^m_Multi = 1/(2r_x m) - \alpha/(2(1-\alpha) \times Z) \quad (13).$$

As $m < 1$ and is declining in number of journals it follows that F^m_Multi exceeds F and increases with the number of available journals. Moreover, if by chance journals occasionally fails to take F into account then, in the limit, F^m necessarily equals zero when journal submissions are costless. Consequently, given the seemingly exponential growth of journal outlets in recent years it follows that effective resistance to the testing of implausible null hypotheses has likely dropped considerably, possibly to levels where almost everything they publish concerns $F = 100\%$ null hypotheses.

5. Further Applications

The presented model has several further implications for issues often addressed by critical engagements with significance testing practice and malpractice. Here I discuss some of the more salient ones.

5.1 P-Hacking

A matter of broad concern is researcher reporting practices that, in effect, bias reported p-values downward. P-hacking is a widely recognized driver of false positive outcomes concern (e.g., Principle 3 of the *ASA Statement*; Hail et al., 2020; Chen, 2021; Gow, 2024). While it takes many forms the effective impact is the same. The researcher reports a finding as if they are using a conventionally accepted α such as 5% when, in fact, they are truly using some (undisclosed and commonly unknowable) higher significance threshold in reaching these determinations. In the

context of this analysis's equation (2) hypothesis selection maximization objective, p-hacking equates to increasing α (but not disclosing it). Taken to the extreme p-hacking is argued to provide a pathway to "presenting anything as significant" (Simmons et al., 2010).

Under endogenous selection increasing α increases researcher interest in selecting plausible rather than implausible hypotheses (equation 4c). However, the simple fact that, *ceteris paribus*, it is far easier to successfully hack a false hypothesis than a true one surely tempers such interest. In fact, as p-hacking does increase journal novelty content, a case can be made that when practiced in moderation it could benefit the overall research relevance of a journal or field mired in a sub-40% implausibility resistance wasteland. It also bears mentioning that p-hacking works in reverse as well. When journals implicitly or explicitly mandate that significance findings hold across multiple tests effective α falls. For instance, the simple requirement that a study confirm a significance outcome with a second such outcome from a holdout sample (as proposed by Ohlson, 2022) effectively replaces α with α^2 . In many fields journal mandated reverse p-hacking is a requisite component of the publication process. While reverse p-hacking has much to recommend it as a means of controlling false positive content, its application comes at a price of lower test of hypothesis novelty content.⁷

5.2 Hypothesis Bundles

A commonly encountered significance testing integrity concern arises when researchers engage in the contemporaneous testing of bundles of hypotheses, a practice which I broadly identify as *En Masse* hypothesis testing (e.g., Ionnidis, 2019; Johnson, 2016; Gelman and Loken, 2014). Nominally, the analysis's hypothesis selection model readily accommodates the availability of such bundles. Instead of just having the option to select stand-alone hypotheses the researcher has the

⁷ Appendix C provides selection determined research frontier and journal content outcomes conditional on Z, r, and F when p-thr is set at 20% (consistent with p-hacking prevalence) and 1% (consistent with reverse p-hacking net dominance).

further option of choosing a hypothesis bundle to test from a vast frontier of available bundles based on representative (e.g., mean) F and Z values for the hypotheses contained in each bundle. Under such conditions researchers prefer testing bundles with higher representative F and Z values subject to journal resistance on the F dimension in much the same manner as they choose which hypotheses to test on a hypothesis-by-hypothesis basis. Moreover, in research environments wherein there is every expectation that tested nulls be inherently implausible “nil” conjectures it readily follows that researchers will have little difficulty in locating such high F bundles. Such a bundle selection preference extends to even the most unscrupulous ones among them, those whose research strategy is the identification of some expansive data set followed by the existence tests of every feasible correlation within it.

At the broader selection frontier level hypothesis bundling does put in play factors that possibly make the testing of plausible hypotheses more attractive, an attraction that may truly breathes life into perils of *en masse* hypothesis testing narratives.⁸ Consider, for example, a setting wherein a researcher interested in testing hypothesis A collects data and is deciding upon whether or not to invest in a design and collect the data necessary to test it. It so happens that this same data and design enable the testing of two additional hypotheses of research interest, B and C, as well at zero incremental time, cost, and effort. Suppose further that all three are equally implausible. It then follows that producing the odds of a rejection outcome for at least one of the three hypothesis tests rises to $1-(1-F)^3 > F$. Journal implausibility resistance, assuming the journal has no knowledge or takes no account of the multiple hypothesis nature of things, will be based on F , not $1-(1-F)^3$. So, the researcher ends up implicitly testing a relatively implausible null hypothesis that all three hypotheses are true while appearing to test a far more plausible stand-alone hypothesis.

The preceding illustration reveals how hypothesis bundles lower the risk of failing to produce

⁸ At $Z = 80\%$ the level of F needed to tip the publication balance in favor of more false than true positives is just under 10%.

a significance outcome from a given level of research effort while raising the prospects of a favorable journal outcome from that effort. Consequently, their availability attenuates researcher incentives to test truly high F , on a stand-alone basis, hypotheses. However, there are reasons to think that this attenuation may not be that great. Firstly, as mentioned previously, in many fields “nil” hypothesis testing is the expectation and as Cohen (1993) forcefully argues, such hypotheses are almost always *per se* implausible. Hence, the researcher may well find themselves facing a feasible opportunity set entirely consisting of high F bundles and so will choose their bundles accordingly.

Secondly, even in fields where low F bundles are an option, it remains the case that bundling’s attractiveness very much depends on the cost per hypothesis test reduction achieved from it. Adding another hypothesis to form or augment a bundle number is almost always costly in terms of time and effort, thereby putting a cost constraint in place. The researcher must now factor in the incremental cost of pursuing an additional hypothesis versus in deciding whether it makes sense to add another hypothesis into the mix. In fact, when costs rise in direct proportion to the number of hypotheses in the bundle then researchers will always find it more advantageous to simply treat each hypothesis, be it found in a bundle or by itself, as a stand-alone proposition and would select hypotheses in line with equation (3).

Thirdly, researchers may broadly resist taking the *En Masse* bundling path because of anticipated journal resistance to publication conditional on their awareness of the multiple hypothesis origins of the *En Masse* nature of investigations. At the extreme, journals or the researchers themselves may impose conventional multiple test adjustments to significance threshold levels. For instance, under the well-known Bonferroni adjustment the chosen standalone test significance threshold (commonly .05) is divided by the number of hypotheses tested. From a hypothesis selection perspective imposing such a correction greatly reduces the attractiveness of testing large bundles of hypothesis as opposed to standalone hypotheses or bundles consisting of just a few a

priori curated hypotheses. On a more informal basis it also follows that journals will proactively resist the publishing studies revealed or suspected to be produced by means of *En Masse* testing strategies based on how low rather than how high the tested hypotheses F values are thought to be.

5.3 De-Emphasis of Significance Outcomes

A longstanding concern with significance test based inference is the central role played by “statistically significant” in determining research success. Equation (2) reflects this centrality as F and $H(y)$ only matter if a test outcome is “statistically significant.” Absent significance, publication will not occur, regardless of how large $H(y)$ or F happen to be. Proposed practices for remedying this overemphasis on significance focus on providing pathways to publication success that, in effect, allow $H(y)$ and F to influence publication prospects independent from statistical significance outcome. Such practices include encouraging publication of studies reporting absence of significance outcomes or pre-committing to publication based purely on $H(y)$, F) by means of registered reports. Implementation of such significance attenuation necessarily lowers the statistical significance outcome risk of testing plausible null hypotheses. Hence, apart from hypotheses where prospects of being false are highly remote, the relative attractiveness of taking on plausible nulls increases. Under these conditions endogenous selection suggests that researchers will respond by shifting to the testing more plausible hypotheses. Consequently, the adoption of such practices favors false positive prevalence. So, it is a mistake to think that such strategies necessarily improve the reliability of significant testing inferences.

5.4 Replication

In recent years the absence of replicative assessment of existent significance test based findings in many fields has become a matter of concern. As the production of false positives is inherent to significance testing inference such absence implies that absent replication validation a field surely suffers from widespread erroneous understandings of phenomena of research interest.

Or, so the thinking goes. Endogenous selection, however, suggests a rather different take on the matter.

As a test of hypothesis exercise, a replication analysis nominally retests the hypothesis tested by the study it seeks to replicate. However, a replication (career enhancing) success outcome is not a confirmatory rejection of this same hypothesis. Rather, success lies in making an evidential case that favors this hypothesis being true rather than false. So, it is the original null hypothesis's plausibility (1-F) updated for the identification of further evidence from the original "finding" that guides success-minded researcher interest in replication. So, minimally, a field of study equilibrium F^m in excess of .5 implies sub .5 replication Fs. That is, as F^m rises replication hypothesis choices become increasingly unattractive. And, an F^m of .9 implies sub .1 replication Fs.⁹ Consequently, as journal resistance intensity determines F^m , absence of replication identifies its ineffectiveness. Or, in governing replication verbiage—it suggests a field in the throes of a "resistance crisis" rather than a "replication crisis."

5.5 Power conditioned p-value threshold adjustment

Numerous commentators across many fields of study argue that failure to adjust p-value thresholds in response to research design power is a severe shortcoming of significance testing practice (Ohslon 2015; Kim, Ahmed, and Ji 2018). The essence of the p-value adjustment argument is that lowering α as design power rises better balances type I error with type II error risk. Or, equivalently such adjustment minimizes overall inferential error (from combined type I and type II error). It also impedes the manifestation of Jeffrey's-Lindely paradox conditions wherein significance outcomes are possibly more supportive of the null being true rather than false.

Endogenous selection's relevance to α value adjustment stems from how hypothesis

⁹ Figure 2A in Higginson and Munfro (2015) makes a similar point, but in reverse. Specifically, it illustrates how researcher voluntary (as opposed to mandated) interest in pursuing low F "exploratory" analyses requires the penalization of higher F "confirmatory" analyses. (Penalties are in three forms—a one exploratory hypothesis test buy in, higher cost to conduct confirmatory analyses, and lower rewards for confirmatory relative to exploratory findings.)

implausibility affects Type I and Type II error prevalence. Given F , the likelihood of a Type I error equals $\alpha*(1-F)$ while Type II error likelihood equals $(1-Z)x(1-\alpha)F$. As hypothesis implausibility increases Type I error prevalence decreases while Type II error prevalence increases. In other words, at high F levels one rarely encounters the high Type I low Type II error rate environment where tightening significance thresholds is beneficial. Consequently, it follows that absent substantive implausibility resistance there is little point to p-value tightening. Moreover, even should power attain a level sufficient to create the sorts of conditions where p-value tightening is advisable (e.g., the Type I/Type II error rate exceeds 1), it provides inconsequential improvement in terms of overall error reduction. For instance, in the 50% resistance in combination with 99.9% power-based research frontier outcomes reported in table 3, when F and Z are both high overall error borders on non-existent. Consequently, the improvement in reliability gain from tightening α is similarly vacuous.

6 Conclusion

Leamer (1978) differentiates statistics which addresses “the theory of inferences *ideally* drawn from data” from “metastatistics” which is “the theory of inferences *actually* drawn from data.” (p. v) This study falls very much within the metastatistics domain. It develops a comprehensive picture of what actually transpires in statistical significance assessment practices and illustrates the central roles that implausibility resistance and researcher success incentives play in it. When implausibility resistance is strong or success incentives are weak, commonly encountered concerns about “statistical significance” outcome reliability (i.e., that it produces false positives in numbers) have traction. Otherwise, they don’t. Moreover, there are solid reasons for thinking that in many research settings success incentives are strong, not weak, and implausibility resistance is weak, not strong. There is an abundance of observational evidence in support of such thinking. Such evidence includes absence of serious article engagement with the case for thinking its tested nulls are true,

widespread testing of non-existence nulls when existence is not in question, and non-testing of absence of clinical/economic/behavioral consequence nulls when such consequence is truly what is in question.¹⁰ So, is it that surprising that significance testing practitioners in such fields pay little heed to frantic declarations regarding the unreliability of “statistical significance” outcomes that pertain to plausible null hypotheses that they rarely test?

The study also identifies absence of engagement with even passingly plausible null hypotheses as a matter that merits as much concern and attention as significance testing’s conditional vulnerability to widespread false positive prevalence. Doing nothing much besides producing clever demonstrations that implausible conjectures are implausible is not a recipe for advancing knowledge or understanding of phenomena of interest. Moreover, mistaken notions about the reliability of statistical significance identifications are very much a hindrance to a field addressing this concern. Actions taken to address phantom false positive threats to the reliability of statistical significance identifications incentivize researchers to increase the vigor with which they pursue the testing of implausible nulls. Consequently, seemingly counterintuitive actions such as raising significance thresholds (even via p-hacking) and minimizing robustness assessment requirements can substantially improve the collective relevance of a field’s research findings while adding little in the way of false positive risk.

More broadly, the analysis illustrates the importance of understanding significance test based assessment of evidence from an overall process perspective. A process wherein participant behavior is largely governed by two offsetting forces: (1) a significance outcome mandate that is rigorously enforced by means of accepted statistical significance thresholds; and (2) a relatively nebulous

¹⁰ Goodman et al. (2019), in fact, formalize the oft-encountered practice of pairing a significance test of an equals zero hypothesis with an effect size assessment of whether the estimated effect size exceeds a specified consequence threshold. Hence, the significance assessment is applied to a comparatively less plausible null while the more plausible null is effectively assessed using a 50% α level. Relatedly, Fitzpatrick et al. (2024) apply this notion to identify false positive prevalence in their model of the interplay between significance thresholds and researcher p-hacking levels.

expectation/hope/desire that such statistical significance outcomes surprise. When these two forces are reasonably balanced significance test assessment provides generally reliable “findings” that are of considerable inferential relevance. When they are not the wheels fall off. Analyses produce outcomes that either greatly surprise but are not trustworthy or are quite trustworthy but do not truly surprise.

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Appendix A

Research Frontier and Journal Content Calculations

The table 1 research frontier and journal content outcomes conditional on F, Z, α , and r are as follow:

Figure A1
Research Frontier and Journal Content Outcome Calculations

Outcome	Calculation ¹¹
Research Frontier	
Implausibility(F)	Exogenously Specified in table 1, in tables 2 and 3 it is $1/(2r)-\alpha/(2(1-\alpha)\times Z)$, Min 0, Max 1, in table 4 it is $1/(4r)-\alpha/(2(1-\alpha)\times Z)$
Overall Error	$(1-F)\alpha + (1-\alpha)F_x(1-Z)$
Type II Error	$(1-\alpha)F_x(1-Z)$
Type I Error	$(1-F)\alpha$
Type I/II Ratio	$(1-F)\alpha/[(1-\alpha)F_x(1-Z)]$
Yield	$\alpha + (1-\alpha)Z_xF$
Journal	
Hypothesis Novelty ¹⁵	$(1-F)$
False Positive %	$(1-F)\alpha/[\alpha + (1-\alpha)F_xZ]$ ¹²

- α is the journal determined threshold for identifying significant test outcomes as “statistically significant”;
- F is the (possibly perceived) prior odds that the tested null hypothesis is false;
- Z reflects the employed test’s incremental efficacy at rejecting false nulls given α ;
- r reflects resistance to publication conditional on F.

¹¹ Obtained values are determined conditional on the null being a point value. If, instead, the null is presumed to be a range of values (e.g., a hypothesis that the parameter is less than or equal to zero), then the reported overall error, type I error, type I/II ratio, and false positive % values identify upper limits.

¹⁵ In the case of uniform priors, a further adjustment is made to account for the fact that F has a uniform distribution over the interval from 0 to 1. *Ceteris paribus*, the odds of obtaining a significance outcome rise with F. Consequently, tests of high F hypotheses are more likely to clear the journal’s α screen. Resistance to high F hypotheses, on the other hand, offsets this effect by screening out high F hypotheses. In these conditions the F for purposes of determining novelty content is:

$$F = \{Z(1-\alpha)(1/3 - r/5) + \alpha(1/2 - 7r/24)\} / \{(1/2 - r/4)\times(1-\alpha)Z + \alpha(1-r/2)\}$$

¹² In the case of uniform priors this ratio is calculated as:

$$FP\% = \alpha(1/2)\times(1 - r/4) / \{((1/2) - r/4)\times(1 - \alpha)\times Z + \alpha(1/2 - 3r/8)\}$$

Appendix B

The presented research frontier and journal outcomes presume a scalar relation between resistance and hypothesis implausibility. Another reasonable perspective, however, is that resistance increases at an increasing rate with implausibility. Hence, resistance strengthens rapidly as F approaches 1. A straightforward analytically tractable representation of such resistance is to redefine the journal's ideal resistance function as $J(F) = F^2$.¹³

Here again a journal never publishes studies addressing *a priori* false (i.e., $F = 1$) hypotheses when $r=100\%$. However, resistance dissipates more rapidly than linear resistance as F declines, in line with the idea that while hypothesis implausibility may matter greatly to a journal when F is near 1, but matters less when F is not proximate to 1.

When facing a journal employing squared resistance in its submission evaluations the success maximizing hypothesis implausibility level at $r=100\%$ is:

$$F^M = \{(\alpha^2 + 2Z^2(1-\alpha)^2)^{1/2} - \alpha\} / \{2Z(1-\alpha)\} \quad (B1)$$

Table B1 presents research frontier and journal content outcomes based for this constrained optimization setting for resistance levels ranging from 50% to super resistance.

¹³ In general the value of r where seeking to test $F^m = 1$ hypotheses emerges as the optimal strategy drops as the value of the exponent applied to F rises. H

Table B1
Research Frontier and Journal Outcomes for $J(F) = F^2$

Attribute	Z			
	30%	50%	80%	99.9%
Corner r's	42.5%	45.3%	45.9%	47.5%
<i>Panel A: 50% Resistance</i>				
Overall Error	61.3%	45.3%	18.5%	0.2%
Type II Error	60.9%	45.1%	18.4%	0.01%
Type I Error	0.4%	0.2%	0.1%	0.19%
Type I/II Ratio	0.007	0.004	0.005	19
Journal Hypothesis Novelty	8.5%	5.1%	3.2%	2.6%
Journal False Positive %	1.35%	0.51%	0.21%	0.13%
<i>Panel B: 75% Resistance</i>				
Overall Error	50.1%	37.5%	16.0%	1.1%
Type II Error	48.8%	36.4%	14.9%	0.1%
Type I Error	1.3%	1.1%	1.1%	1%
Type I/II Ratio	0.03	0.03	0.07	10
Journal Hypothesis Novelty	26.7%	23.4%	21.6%	20.9%
Journal False Positive %	5.14%	2.83%	1.67%	1.31%
<i>Panel C: 100% Resistance</i>				
Overall Error	43.4%	32.9%	14.4%	1.7%
Type II Error	41.5%	31.2%	12.8%	.06%
Type I Error	1.9%	1.7%	1.6%	1.6%
Type I/II Ratio	0.05	0.05	0.13	27
Journal Hypothesis Novelty	37.5%	34.4%	32.5%	29.9%
Journal False Positive %	8.2%	4.7%	2.9%	2.3%
<i>Panel D: Super-Resistance</i>				
Overall Error	22.0%	18.0%	9.5%	3.4%
Type II Error	18.4%	14.5%	6.1%	0.03%
Type I Error	3.6%	3.5%	3.4%	3.37%
Type I/II Ratio	0.20	0.24	0.58	112
Journal Hypothesis Novelty	72.3%	69.5%	67.8%	67.2%
Journal False Positive %	28.1%	17.8%	11.5%	9.3%

Appendix C

This appendix reports researcher frontier and journal outcomes for overly loose and overly tight statistical significance identification thresholds. The loose threshold level of $p = 20\%$ corresponds to a plausible extreme impact obtainable from researcher p-hacking activities. The tight $p = 1\%$ threshold conservatively reflects the impact of journal and peer requirements that a study present multiple statistical significance outcomes in support of each of its findings.

Table C1
Research Frontier and Journal Outcomes When $\alpha = 20\%$

Attribute	Z			
	30%	50%	80%	99.9%
Corner r's	18.75%	25.0%	44.2%	45.2%
<i>Panel A: 50% Resistance</i>				
Overall Error	41.0%	35.0%	16.6%	2.6%
Type II Error	32.3%	30.0%	13.5%	0.07%
Type I Error	8.7%	5.0%	3.1%	2.53%
Type I/II Ratio	0.269	0.167	0.230	36.1
Journal Hypothesis Novelty	41.7%	25.0%	15.6%	12.5%
Journal False Positive %	24.5%	10.0%	4.2%	2.8%
<i>Panel B: 75% Resistance</i>				
Overall Error	29.0%	28.3%	18.0%	9.2%
Type II Error	14.0%	16.7%	8.2%	0.04%
Type I Error	15.0%	11.6%	9.8%	9.16%
Type I/II Ratio	1.07	0.69	1.20	229
Journal Hypothesis Novelty	75.0%	58.3%	49.0%	45.8%
Journal False Positive %	57.7%	31.8%	18.6%	14.5%
<i>Panel C: 100% Resistance</i>				
Overall Error	23.0%	25.0%	18.6%	12.5%
Type II Error	4.7%	10.0%	5.5%	0.03%
Type I Error	18.3%	15.0%	13.1%	12.47%
Type I/II Ratio	3.89	1.50	2.38	416
Journal Hypothesis Novelty	91.7%	75%	65.6%	52.5%
Journal False Positive %	83.3%	50.0%	31.3%	25.0%
<i>Panel D: Super-Resistance</i>				
Overall Error	20%	20%	19.6%	17.5%
Type II Error	0%	0%	1.5%	~0%
Type I Error	20%	20%	18.1%	17.5%
Type I/II Ratio	-	-	12.1	175,000
Journal Hypothesis Novelty	100%	100%	90.6%	87.5%
Journal False Positive %	100%	100%	69.7%	58.4%

Table C2
Research Frontier and Journal Outcomes at When $\alpha = 1\%$

Attribute	Z			
	30%	50%	80%	99.9%
Corner r's	46.8%	48.1%	48.8%	49.0%
<i>Panel A: 50% Resistance</i>				
Overall Error	68.2%	49.0%	19.7%	0.1%
Type II Error	68.1%	49.0%	19.7%	0.1%
Type I Error	0.1%	~0%	~0%	~0%
Type I/II Ratio	0.001	~0%	~0%	~0%
Journal Hypothesis Novelty	1.7%	1.0%	0.6%	0.5%
Journal False Positive %	0.06%	0.02%	~0%	~0%
<i>Panel B: 75% Resistance</i>				
Overall Error	45.4%	32.8%	13.4%	0.41%
Type II Error	45.0%	32.5%	13.1%	0.07%
Type I Error	0.4%	0.3%	0.3%	0.34%
Type I/II Ratio	0.009	0.009	0.023	4.86
Journal Hypothesis Novelty	35.0%	34.3%	34.0%	33.8%
Journal False Positive %	1.7%	1.0%	0.6%	0.5%
<i>Panel C: 100% Resistance</i>				
Overall Error	34.0%	24.8%	10.3%	0.55%
Type II Error	33.5%	24.3%	9.8%	0.05%
Type I Error	0.5%	0.5%	0.5%	0.5%
Type I/II Ratio	0.015	0.021	0.051	10
Journal Hypothesis Novelty	51.7%	51.0%	50.7%	50.5%
Journal False Positive %	3.4%	2.0%	1.3%	1.0%
<i>Panel D: Super-Resistance</i>				
Overall Error	16.9%	12.6%	5.6%	0.8%
Type II Error	16.2%	11.9%	4.8%	0.02%
Type I Error	0.7%	0.7%	0.8%	0.78%
Type I/II Ratio	0.043	0.059	0.167	39
Journal Hypothesis Novelty	76.7%	76.0%	75.6%	75.5%
Journal False Positive %	9.7%	5.9%	3.7%	3.0%